

Observing merging of any two profiles, of any particular individual in, any particular social domains,platforms, or websites.

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Abstract:

In internet, generally in social networking sites, or social domains, any user can create multiple accounts, as per their conviniency. Recently, Facebook too is found to be providing, service features for merging of pages. Similarly Linkedin too is found to be providing service for merging any two profiles.

Introduction:

For me, merging of two profiles, means, merging accounts of same person, and I don't know, if any two different users too would be allowed to be merged or not, to which question beginning from privacy and lot of topics including understanding would come which then would be talked like as server and clients, or two clients(users) using some profiles, with complete services provided, for both users with access. That would be like as merging of two different companies, thus, I thought to write, what I do understand by means of merging profiles.

Thus, let us begin with any two profiles, by taking example of author's own profiles. I have two profiles in facebook, one with username arjundahal001, and another with arjundahalard. If we woul talk about merging, as simply merging, then two those accounts can be merged, infact easily merged.

Merging Process:

Now, let us observe what happens during merging. I would be asked about username once again, and that would be or wouldn't be, based on two previous usernames;i.e. arjundahal001, and arjundahalard. I might be allowed to use, any two among them, or new, which would depend entirely upon, platform allowing us to merge profiles. Then problems comes during merging, is about date and time, as per our

uploads in our profiles. For an example, I have uploaded lot of similiar photographs in both of my user profile, which would mean, date and time, as well as duplicateness needs to be studied.

That is still not sufficient, because I might have wrote different statuses in two profiles for same pictures, which again still creates a problem. Then problem again comes in features like comments, and emojis, as per statuses, as per date and time, and as per fellows, because I mightn't have completely same friends in both facebook accoounts.

That was a problem which further does arises, when we have to merge chats and conversations, and that too, based on date and time, between any two profiles.

Alternative Process:

Since merging of statuses, studying duplicateness, then again studying based on date and time, would be tougher work, more simpler mechanism can be used, and that is by introducing, merged feature, where, after profiles are merged, only one username is available, but under that username, like as of nodes or branches, two or more than two profiles can be placed. That would be convinient means as work on date and time would be reduced, where as our datas would be as they were, and merged feature would just ask about our accounts to be discussed.

For an example, we mostly use mobile numbers and emails for creating accounts, and in single cellphone, we can have lot of accounts even I do have 3 Google accounts (Gmail), which does allows me to work, as per my email preferences, or email that I like to use more frequently. Merging those three emails into one, would still need, some account unique, to represent merging of those three accounts.

Outcomes:

When merging of profiles is successfully done, then, it can be expanded between any two different persons, and their profiles. Common example can be talked about husband and wife, who would like to have single profile in their facebook, to be used. That would mean profile would be a couple's profile. If we extend it further, then it can be made like even for a family.

Problems in such types of accounts would come in privacy, because I might speak frankly, to one of couple, but not to other, and that would create problem in social life, and same would happen even for family accounts.

Conclusion:

For two account of any same individual, if merged as per date and time, would be best, as that would allow to have one good account. For couples and families, or for any organization, branches and nodes can be made. Those features too can be found, in most of social platform, beginning from some unique profile, which then serves like as server, to establish clients, and It would depend upon our work, to merge two different profiles of same person.

Questions: Why peoples do open more then one account?

It would depend upon individual peoples, to discuss why peoples do open more then one accounts in any social platform, as some like to flirt, some would talk about social status, shyness, privacy, and some would even talk like as of having branches to rely on social network.

Inquiring further would be like as why do people have more than one account, like as I have email of Google, Yahoo, Microsoft, CERN(Protonmail), and do have twitter account, Linkedin account, Instagram account, and much more, and among them, I use only few, as we all prefer services and preferences.

Services like as broadcasting and distributing same news, stories, views to particular accounts too can be found, and serves well when we have multiple accounts or need to post contents at places, which in general langauges are talked as subscribers and followers, to keep them up to date, as per news of any topics.

Actknowledgements:

My actknowledgement goes to various websites and their pages, as well as FAQ(Frequently Asked Questions) section, as I do read somerimes. I haven't wrote any references for this paper, as not citing my own work, would seem, quite unfaithful to myself, though, it is practised and needed.

In earlier papers, topics of Standarization of addresses, as well as lot of topics, would again be needed to be studied and discussed for this paper, when merging of any two accounts are done, due to topics of path, or link, which would put question again.